

IMSF Workgroup Seminar Series - Instrumentation

Harnessing the power of the unreduced data in FTMS

... or how to squeeze out maximum information from ion signals

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FTMS: Fourier Transform Mass Spectrometry

- Ion identity (m/z) is encoded as a frequency of ion oscillations in an ion trap
- Frequencies of ion oscillations are measured as time-domain signals (**transients**)
- Fourier transform (FT) decodes transients to reveal frequencies (m/z) values

Electrostatic field-based

Orbitrap

Orbitrap™ families: LTQ Orbitrap; Exactive; Q Exactive; Exploris; Fusion; Lumos; Eclipse

Magnetic field-based

Ion Cyclotron Resonance (ICR) Magnetic Resonance MS (MRMS)

FTMS is the highest resolution & mass accuracy MS technique

FTMS Information Output

Unreduced data
full information content

Reduced data
10-fold smaller file size

metabolites
identified & quantified

proteins
identified & quantified

% sequence coverage in
protein structural analysis

confidence for precursor
and product ion detection

The use of the unreduced data aims to provide performance improvement

The Unreduced Data in FTMS

- I. The Unreduced Data in FTMS
- II. Data Reduction Approaches
- III. How to Get and Process the Unreduced Data
- IV. Examples of Applications

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The Unreduced Data Types in FTMS

Time-domain ion signals (transients)

FT
→

Absorption mode mass spectra

- $R \sim T$ • Resolution increases linearly with transient length (detection period)
- $S/N \sim \sqrt{T}$ • Sensitivity increases as a sqrt of transient length (detection period)

Transients & aFT mass spectra provide equal information output

Time-Domain Ion Signal: Transient

The Unreduced Data

Three components to define a wave:

- Frequency
- Magnitude (measure of amplitude)
- **Phase (angle)**

- example: two waves of the same frequency and amplitude, but different phase

Absorption Mode FT (aFT) Mass Spectrum

The Unreduced Data

aFT preserves all information:

- Frequency
- Amplitude
- Phase

noise (+ and -)

peakbypeak
FTMS DATA ANALYSIS

Simulation of FTMS data:
DOI: 10.1021/jasms.0c00190

Simulations: IMSF, $[M+H]^+$, 497.2 m/z , Orbitrap Q Exactive, 15k @ 200 m/z

Why Reduce FTMS Data?

- **The unreduced data file size:**
 - a single transient: 1-20 MB;
 - a single unreduced mass spectrum: 2-40 MB
 - a single imaging/LC-MS run: **1-50 GB**
- **Technological challenges/cost**
 - High-performance electronics for transient acquisition
 - Real-time digital signal processing algorithms (on a chip)
 - Efficient software tools for post-processing of “big data”
- **Ease of use**
 - Extended data processing time for the unreduced data processing
 - A larger storage space is needed for the unreduced data

Cost of Reducing FTMS Data?

- **It is a one way street**
 - Once data is reduced, the full data cannot be recovered
 - (Unless the original data is also saved – defeating the purpose)
- **Data reduction always loses information/capability**
 - Spectral quality
 - Unresolved components
 - Noise distribution
 - Unexpected analytes
 - Sub-threshold peaks
 - *Etc.*

Note: the reduced data use is sufficient for many FTMS applications

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Data Reduction Approaches in FTMS

- Transient length: ion detection during a reduced period of time
(*not* all time ions induce signals)
- Calibration of initial phases: post-processing instead of in real time
- Performing other modes of FT: magnitude (mFT) or enhanced (eFT)
 - Noise reduction/thresholding: full vs. reduced profile
 - Visible mass (m/z) range: low and high mass cut-off
 - Centroiding mass spectra
 - Deisotoping, deconvolution
 - Transients are not stored, typically

FTMS Data Hierarchy: Information vs. File Size

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How to Get & Process the Unreduced FTMS Data

- via high-performance external DAQ system: **FTMS Booster**

JASMS 2020, 31, 257-266
DOI: 10.1021/jasms.9b000

Overcoming the technological limitations in acquiring phased & full transients

FTMS Booster: a high-performance DAQ system

- Analogue transient capture after the original built-in pre-amplifier
- Phase artefact-free digitization (sampling) of transients
- Ability to maximize the duty cycle of ion detection event (throughput)
- Ability to record (much) longer transients (due to enhanced flexibility)
- Transient storage (.H5 files) for post-processing, reduced file size

FPGA: field programmable gate array (chip)

Phased Transients: Initial Phases All Close to Zero

Un-phased transients (state of the art)

Phased transients

Mass spectra computed as:
FT real component (aFT)
FT magnitude (mFT)

To be an aFT spectrum,
 this spectrum needs
 phase correction

Phases equal to zeros:
 peaks look up.
 This spectrum is already
 an aFT spectrum

Shown for
 Orbitraps
 ICR/MRMS

Software Requirements for Processing of the «Big Data»

- Processing of any size and number of transients: user-defined FT parameters
- Mass spectra generation in absorption mode FT (aFT): vs. the eFT & mFT (e.g., RAW)
- Processing of any size & number of mass spectra (e.g., RAW in reduced & full profile)
- Processing of mass spectra (e.g., RAW) from different experiments (e.g., tech. replicates)
- Transient-mediated accurate simulation of FTMS data (*DOI: 10.1021/jasms.0c00190*)
- Data analysis of mass spectra (e.g., RAW) using the accurately simulated FTMS data

Peak-by-Peak software package (Spectroswiss) fulfills these requirements

Another Example of the «Big Data» FTMS Software

AutoVectis

- Suite of MS data (post) processing modules
- Uses transient as starting point – unreduced data!
- Can be combined into many different workflows
 - **AutoPhaser** – aFT mode processing
 - **AutoPiquer** – peak picking
 - **AutoSeequer** – top-down assignment
 - **Discharger** – deconvolution & decomposition
 - **AutoLogis** – DOM and petroleomics:

David Kilgour

10.1016/j.marchem.2021.103955

Streamlined
recalibration

aFT image
reprocessing

TOF import

aFT fine
structure

Deconvolution
Decomposition

aFT peak
detection

Top down
sequencing

DOM/Oil
Assignment

<https://www.kilgourlab.com/>

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Examples of Applications

Small molecules (metabolites/peptides)

Data averaging: sensitivity & quantitation accuracy

Full transients: ultra-high resolution, throughput

Transient post-processing: super-resolution algorithms

Large molecules (proteins)

Data averaging: top-down & middle-down sequencing

Transient post-processing: enhanced spectral quality

Transient post-processing: single ion counting

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Benefits of the Unreduced Data: Full Profile Averaging

Srzentic et al., Anal. Chem. (2018) 12527

Enhanced Protein Sequencing with Top/Middle-Down

2D Data Averaging: Use of Multiple LC-MS/MS Technical Replicates

Srzentic *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.* (2018) 12527; Fornelli *et al.*, *J. Proteomics* (2017) 67

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Data Post-Processing for Improved Protein Analysis

Experiment: Fornelli et al., *J. Proteome Res.* 2017, 16, 609–618

Simulations: DOI: 10.1021/jasms.0c00190

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Single Ion Counting: Resolving Protein Interference

- Detection of single ions reduces space charge artefacts (peak interference), but hides peak's charge state

- Charge state of a single ion peak can be deduced from its transient, *e.g.*, via STORI (I2MS)

Williams, Kelleher, Heck

DOI: 10.1038/s41592-020-0764-5

DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.9b01669

STORI: Selective Temporal Overview of Resonant Ions, DOI: 10.1021/jasms.8b06253

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Example: Isotopic Ratio Analysis of Uranium (UO_2)

Extreme spectral dynamic range is required (with high IR precision): 1: 20 000

Averaging of the Unreduced Data: UO₂

LS-APGD

Orbitrap™

External DAQ

**8000 scans
data averaging**

$$\frac{I(^{234}\text{UO}_2)}{I(^{238}\text{UO}_2)} \approx 0.000045$$

Markus et al., JASMS, in print

Example: Quantitation of Trace-Level Compounds

2, 3, 4, 7, 8 – hexachlorodibenzo-dioxin

Electron Impact
Q Exactive GC
60k @ 200 m/z

Challenge: quantitatively accurate analysis of diluted samples (low abundance)

2D Averaging in GC-MS: Sensitivity & Accuracy

1.0 pg solution

100.0 fg solution

10 GC-MS runs averaged data

- Reduced data: .RAW mass spectra (eFT, reduced profile)

- Unreduced data: .H5 mass spectra (aFT, full profile), or transients

JASMS 2020, 31, 257-266

Increased sensitivity is provided by the unreduced data, improved LOD/LOQ

Examples of Applications

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resolution, throughput

Transient post-processing:
super-resolution algorithms

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& middle-down sequencing

Transient post-processing:
enhanced spectral quality

Transient post-processing:
single ion counting

Upgraded Imaging Platform @ Leach Labs

- LTQ Orbitrap XL (mFT)
- MALDI ion source *Spectrograph*
- Data acquisition system

Benefits of Longer Transients and aFT

Dynamic Range = 625 : 1

MALDI Orbitrap XL SM(d16:1/18:0)
15_brain_100k [C₃₉H₇₉N₂O₆P + K]⁺
Scan #7354

PC(32:0)
[C₄₀H₈₀NO₈P + K]⁺

See 21 T FT-ICR MS data: Smith et al., Anal. Chem. 2020 *m/z*

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Super-resolution algorithms:
2-4 fold shorter transients vs. aFT

Protein Quantitation: TMT Complementary Ions (TMTc)

Multiplexed Tandem Mass Tag (TMT) proteomics on Fusion Lumos (HCD)

TMT reporter ions

$T_{acq} = 1.0 \text{ s, eFT}$
 $T_{acq} = 3.0 \text{ s, aFT}$

TMTc (complementary) ions

6 mDa/(z-1)

6 mDa/(z-1)

Precursor:
511.327, z=2

TMTc approach:
Martin Wuehr
(Princeton University)

Speed Up TMTc with Least-Squares Fitting (LSF)

Orbitrap Fusion Lumos™

External DAQ system

#2287
638.386 m/z
 $z=2$

- aFT, $T_{acq} = 3\text{ s}$
- aFT, $T_{acq} = 0.5\text{ s}$
- LSF, $T_{acq} = 0.5\text{ s}$

TMTc approach:
Martin Wuehr
(Princeton University)

Speed Up Imaging: Targeted Metabolite/Drug Analysis

So, When to Use the Unreduced Data?

- Higher spectral dynamic range is required: data averaging across multiple scans
- Ultra-high resolution is required: ion detection during all the time ion signal rings
- Higher sensitivity is required: data averaging across multiple scans & multiple LC/GC-MS runs; data averaging of selected areas in single cell imaging
- Higher throughput is required: enhanced ion detection duty cycle due to parallel ion detection and ion manipulation (fragmentation, accumulation, *etc.*)
- Spectral complexity is beyond the conventional approaches: single ion counting, super-resolution

Always! But benefits differ between applications – to evaluate pros & cons

Summary: Empowering FTMS with The Unreduced Data

Full profile
aFT

Full profile
eFT/mFT

Reduced profile
eFT/mFT

Centroided

- The two equal (!) types of the unreduced data in FTMS: **transients** and **absorption mode** mass spectra
- Advances in hardware and software enabled overcoming the technological challenges & creating the required tools for the unreduced data generation and handling
- Applied benefits: enhanced analytical characteristics for selected (especially multi-scan) applications & enabling the new ones: single ion counting, super-resolution MS, ...
- Current inhibitors: storage space for the unreduced data; computational speed for super-resolution data processing

The unreduced data and tools are now available to advance FTMS applications

Empowering FTMS with The Unreduced Data

Suggested Reading

- Resource on Orbitrap models design and applications: <https://planetorbitrap.com/>
- Advanced fundamentals in Fourier transform mass spectrometry: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-814013-0.00005-3>
- Enhanced Fourier transform for Orbitrap mass spectrometry: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijms.2014.05.019>
- Absorption mode Fourier transform for FTMS: <http://www.kilgourlab.com/absorption-mode-for-ft-ms/>
- Transient-Mediated Simulations of FTMS Isotopic Distributions and Mass Spectra to Guide Experiment Design and Data Analysis: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.0c00190>
- Fourier transform mass spectrometry at the uncertainty principle limit for improved qualitative and quantitative molecular analyses (PhD thesis, Anton Kozhinov): <https://infoscience.epfl.ch/record/205045>
- Trace-Level Persistent Organic Pollutant Analysis with Gas-Chromatography Orbitrap Mass Spectrometry - Enhanced Performance by Complementary Acquisition and Processing of Time-Domain Data: <https://doi.org/10.1021/jasms.9b00032>
- Improved Uranium Isotope Ratio Analysis in the Liquid Sampling-Atmospheric Pressure Glow Discharge/Orbitrap FTMS Coupling Through the Use of an External Data Acquisition System: *by Marcus et al., JASMS, in print*

Questions? Ideas? Most welcome to discuss: tsybin@spectroswiss.ch

Thank you!

<https://topspec.ki.se/>

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David Kilgour

